

Synthesis of Some New N-Aryl-N¹-Acetylureido/thioureido-2-mercaptobenzimidazoles and Their Biological Activity

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Twenty one N-aryl-N¹-acetylureido/thioureido-2-mercaptobenzimidazoles were synthesised by the condensation of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole with chloroacetyl urea/thiourea in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate and dry acetone. The compounds were evaluated for their antibacterial activity against *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *S. lutea*. Several compounds exhibited significant inhibition.

BENZIMIDAZOLES have been reported to possess wide range of biological activities such as antibacterial¹⁻³, antifungal⁴, antiviral⁵ and anthelmintic⁶. Urea derivatives are also associated with antibacterial^{1,2}, antifungal^{1,3}, anthelmintic^{1,1}, insecticidal^{1,5} and herbicidal^{1,4} activity. In view of these, it was considered of interest to synthesise the title compounds and to evaluate them for their antibacterial action.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

The infrared spectra were determined in KBr pellets on Perkin Elmer 137G spectrometer (ν max cm^{-1}) and nmr spectrum in CDCl_3 on varian A-90D instrument using TMS as internal standard (chemical shift τ ppm). The purity of the compounds was checked on tlc.

2-Mercaptobenzimidazole⁷ (I), aryl ureas⁸, aryl thioureas⁹, chloroacetylureas¹⁰ and thioureas (II) were prepared by the reported methods.

The compounds were prepared by the following scheme :

N-Aryl-N¹-acetylureido/thioureido-2-mercaptobenzimidazoles (III): In a typical method, 0.07 mole of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole and 0.01 mole of

chloroacetylurea were refluxed in dry acetone in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.02 mole) and the reaction mixture was poured into cold water. The compound (III) was filtered and recrystallised from methanol.

The analogous N-aryl-N¹-acetyl thioureido-2-mercaptobenzimidazoles were also prepared adopting the above procedure. The compounds (III) thus synthesised are given in Table 1.

TABLE-1

Compounds III

Sl. No.	X	R	m.p. °C	Analysis% ; Found (Calcd.)		
				N	O	H
1.	O	-H	94	16.96 (17.23)	58.6 (58.9)	4.0 (4.29)
2.	O	-m-CH ₃	220	16.12 (16.47)	59.76 (60.0)	5.0 (4.70)
3.	O	-p-CH ₃	167	16.95 (16.47)	59.56 (60.0)	4.94 (4.70)
4.	O	-o-CH ₃	170	16.78 (16.47)	60.33 (60.0)	4.86 (4.70)
5.	O	-p-OCH ₃	140	15.34 (15.78)	57.55 (57.30)	4.03 (4.49)
6.*	O	-o-OCH ₃	160	16.21 (15.73)	56.98 (57.30)	4.90 (4.49)
7.	O	-m-NO ₂	190	19.02 (18.86)	51.60 (51.75)	3.13 (3.61)
8.	O	-o-NO ₂	195	18.47 (18.86)	52.02 (51.75)	3.26 (3.51)
9.	O	-p-NO ₂	165	18.52 (18.86)	51.98 (51.75)	3.03 (3.51)
10.	O	-2,4(NO ₂) ₂	150	19.87 (20.18)	45.77 (46.15)	2.57 (2.88)
11.	O	-p-Br	225	12.58 (13.32)	47.30 (47.40)	3.07 (3.20)
12.	O	-o-Cl	180	15.02 (15.53)	52.97 (53.25)	3.17 (3.60)
13.	O	-p-Cl	185	15.67 (15.53)	53.72 (53.25)	3.87 (3.60)
14.	O	-m-Cl	140	15.23 (15.53)	53.63 (53.25)	3.77 (3.60)

(Table 1 Contd.)

15.	S	-H	275	16.02 (16.37)	55.97 (56.14)	4.31 (4.09)
16.	S	-p-CH ₃	200	16.32 (16.85)	56.90 (57.30)	4.07 (4.49)
17.	S	-m-CH ₃	205	16.97 (16.85)	57.61 (57.30)	4.93 (4.49)
18†.	S	-p-Cl	175	14.94 (14.87)	50.50 (50.99)	3.0 (3.45)
19.	S	-m-Cl	260	14.37 (14.87)	50.61 (50.99)	3.87 (3.45)
20.	S	-o-Cl	270	14.52 (14.87)	50.77 (50.99)	3.51 (3.45)
21.	S	-p-OCH ₃	255	15.49 (15.05)	54.46 (54.89)	4.70 (4.30)

IR (cm⁻¹) No. 6*. 3350 (NH), 1680 (CONH), 1600 (C=N).
No. 18†. 3000 (NH), 1680 (CONH), 1620 (C=N),
1190 (C=S).

NMR (τ) No. 2. 7.75 (singlet, OH₂), 5.72 (singlet, OH₂), 2.5-3.2
(multiplet, Ar-H), -0.13 (hump, N=C-NH),
-0.88 (hump, -C-NH), -2.63 (hump, -C-NH-C).

 TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF N-ARYL-N¹-
ACETYLUREIDO/THIOUREIDO-2-MERCAPTO-
BENZIMIDAZOLES

Sl. No.	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. lutea</i>
1.	-	-	-
2.	-	-	-
3.	+	-	-
4.	-	-	-
5.	-	-	-
6.	-	-	-
7.	+	+	+
8.	-	+	+
9.	+	+	-
10.	+	+	-
11.	+	+	-
12.	+	+	+
13.	++	++	++
14.	+++	+++	+++
15.	-	-	-
16.	+	-	+
17.	+	-	+
18.	+	-	-
19.	++	-	-
20.	++	-	-
21.	++	-	-
Tetracycline	++++	++++	++++

*Numbering is the same as in Table 1.

Inhibition zones
+ = 5-8 mm.
++ = 9-14 mm.
+++ = 15-20 mm.
++++ = >20 mm.

Antibacterial activity :

All the synthesised compounds were evaluated for their antibacterial activity¹⁶ against *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus* and *S. lutea*, using tetracycline as standard (Table 2). Majority of the compounds inhibited *B. subtilis* to varying extent while a few compounds were found to be active against *S. aureus* and *S. lutea*.

It is evident from the results that all the compounds, (no. 12, 13, 14, 18, 19, 20), substituted by chloro group in aryl nucleus are active against *B. subtilis*.

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